

INTEGRATING VALUES IN EDUCATION: INSIGHTS FROM THE BHAGAVAD GITA

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Paper Received On: 20 May 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 24 June 2024

Published On: 01 July 2024

Abstract

This paper tries to explore the potential of Srimad Bhagavt-Gita for inculcation of values. The present state of value erosion is leading the society towards crimes. As a result murder, theft, corruption, rape and other crimes are increasing day by day. Srimad Bhagavad-Gita is a holy book of Hindu Religion. This knowledge was imparted in a situation of dilemma. It is the form of purest and universal knowledge as it offers solutions to many problems of value crisis. In the present study, our holy book 'Shrimad Bhagavad-Gita' has been critically studied with special reference to value education. The educational ideas in Shrimad Bhagavad-Gita are highly progressive and full of intuitive insight. The present study suggests the methods to change attitude towards moral values, the relevance of philosophy of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita to the problems of value inculcation. verses of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita important for value inculcation among students and Values in teacher student relationship from the perspective of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita.

Keywords: *Bhagavad Gita, Value inculcation, Education, Moral values.*

Introduction

The classical literature especially Upanishads and Bhagavad-Gita are the base of Indian philosophical thought which has contributed immensely in the Indian philosophy of Education. Many countries like India are facing value crisis. Human civilisation cannot be imagined without moral values. Human values are closely integrated with the human life, as they add quality to life. The inability of education system to inculcate values is visible from the fact, that the level of education does not guarantee the moral behaviour. The highly educated persons have been reported to commit crimes and indulge in immoral behaviour. There is need to search for such measures that boost moral behaviour of people. Shrimad Bhagavad Gita cherished the philosophical teachings especially with reference to value

education. Shrimad Bhagavad Gita consists such ideas that are highly progressive and overloaded with potential for value inculcation.

Shrimad Bhagavad Gita

Shrimad Bhagavad Gita, a well known treatise, is a sacred text of Hindus. This is in the form of conversation between Shri Krishna and Arjuna. It was delivered in a situation of dilemma. The knowledge of Shrimad Bhagavat Gita helped Arjuna to come out of that dilemma. The knowlwdge of The Bhagavat Gita is still relevant today (Bisht, 2013; Shrivastva, 2016). Shrimad Bhagavad Gita consists of 18 chapters.

Value Education

The failure of modern education to inculcate values among literates is a matter of great concern. The present state of value erosion is leading the society towards crimes. As a result murder, theft, corruption, rape and other crimes are increasing day by day. More surprising part of the story is that many of these crimes are committed by well educated persons. This indicates the inefficiency of modern education system to values among the literate masses in India. This is due to the unique nature of value education. Values cannot be taught, they are rather imbibed from real life instances.

On the other hand, the ancient education system, which was based on education in Gurukuls was far better on this front. The values among the literate as well as illiterate people of India were exemplary. In these Gurukuls the ancient scriptures were taught. These scriptures were indicative of code of conduct with many instances. Bhagavatgita is one of the main scriptures of Ancient India. After reading the Bhagavad Gita, one can understand the valuable asset of knowledge and it requires deep analysis and interpretation.

However, from the review of research literature, it is observed that very few studies have been conducted on the concept of value education in Shrimad Bhagavat Gita philosophy. The present study is therefore, an attempt to study the concept of value education in the philosophy of Shrimad Bhagavat Gita.

Objectives of the Study

- To explain the relevance of philosophy of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita to the problems of value inculcation.
- To locate the methods to change attitude towards moral values.
- To select verses of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita important for value inculcation among students.
- Values in teacher student relationship from the perspective of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita.

Methods and Procedure

As the present problem chosen for research is primarily philosophical in nature, therefore the investigator has based her study on the philosophical and documentary analysis. The relevant feature of information has been taken from various primary and secondary sources. The primary source of information is relevant material available in the form of the text of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita. The secondary sources in the form of literature produced by many saints and writers, students, magazines, books and multimedia materials etc.

The main approach is analytical, which is called descriptive analytical research. A descriptive research is design to obtain valid, general, conclusions from the facts discovered. The study is philosophical where various books of Shrimad Bhagwad Gita written by various authors were critically analyzed with special reference to the concept of value education.

Discussion

Relevance of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita to the problem of value inculcation

Teaching of the Bhagavad Gita will help to solve the problem of value inculcation among the students as it is the conversation between the teacher and student. Teacher is the maker of the nation; he makes the doctors, engineers, teachers and businessman and above all the good human being. All type of individuals are made by the types of values inculcated by their teachers directly or indirectly. By reading this gospel of Gita teacher should be able to inculcate the values among students by applying the method as Lord Krishna. The Bhagavad Gita encourages one to perform one's obligatory duties as a sacrificial offering to God and not to turn our back upon them. It explains how delusion arises and how one become bound to present conditions, suggesting the various alternatives that are available to one to escape from them. It can be concluded that Shrimad Bhagavad Gita is most relevant for value inculcation. It helps to know the virtues and defects of oneself. Self knowledge helps one to improve the self by the inculcation of values opposite to one's defects in the actions, knowledge and devotion. It helps to inculcate the purity among self (soul) and body by good and spiritual thoughts.

Methods to change attitude towards moral values

Moral values refer to a set of principles that guide an individual on how to evaluate right verses wrong. Moral values are standards of good and evil, which given an individual's behavior and choices. Individual's moral may derive from society and government, religion or self. When moral values derive from society and government, necessity may change as the laws and morals of the society change. An example the impact of changing laws on moral

values may be seen in the case of marriage vs. “living together” relationship. People generally apply moral values to justify decision, intention and actions and it also defines the personal character of a person. An individual with high moral values reflects value of respect, unbiasedness, honesty and compassion.

Shrimad Bhagavad Gita consists of large number of methods to change the attitude towards moral values. So some of the methods which really helpful to change attitude towards moral values are enlisted below:

- Realization of the identity
- Increase the tolerance power
- By regular and proper duties
- Do selfless action
- Self satisfaction
- Control on senses
- Devotion to God
- Be courageous
- Take personal responsibilities
- Be patient
- Be willing to serve
- Take guidance
- Add value to the world
- By destruction of desires and passion
- By keeping customs and traditions as it is
- Have fidelity
- Follow the discipline of meditation
- By destruction of demonian nature
- By penance of speech
- By motivation
- Role reversal
- Story telling method
- Discussion method
- Debates
- Brain storming

Selection of Verses of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita Important For Value Inculcation among Students:

Shrimad Bhagavad Gita has been a source of inspiration and enlightenment for generation. The Gita is not only a message of a general spiritual philosophy; however it has many practical aspects in the application of such principles in our day to day lives.

As we study gospel of Gita we found that Shrimad Bhagavad Gita is a hub of values there are so many verses in it which may help us for value inculcation among students. Verses which help to inculcate the value among students in chapter wise. Sequences are enlisted below:

Sr. No.	Chapter	Verse Number
1	2	2, 3, 6, 7, 11, 14, 15, 16, 17, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 44, 45, 48, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66.
2	3	3, 4, 7, 8, 12, 13, 32, 35, 36.
3	4	11, 15, 20, 30, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39, 40, 42.
4	5	4, 6, 10, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20, 23.
5	6	5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 17, 20, 21, 24, 25, 29, 30, 38, 39, 47.
6	7	4, 5, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18, 27, 29, 30.
7	8	5, 7, 14.
8	9	16, 17, 25, 26, 32, 33.
9	10	3, 14, 17, 18, 28, 39.
10	11	55.
11	12	16, 17, 18, 21.
12	13	1, 5, 6, 7, 33, 34.
13	14	16, 17, 19, 20.
14	16	1, 5, 13, 15, 16, 17.
15	17	4, 15.
16	18	1, 20, 42, 44, 46, 63, 64, 70.

List of the values and their relevant verses showed by Shrimad Bhagavad Gita

Sr. No	Value	Verse No.	Sr. No	Value	Verse No.
1	Truthfulness	2.17, 10.14.	22	Curiosity	6. 38, 39.
2	Quest for knowledge	2. 31, 54, 55, 6. 38, 10. 17, 18. 18.1.	23	Spirit of enquiry	2. 6, 31, 39, 6.39, 10.17,18
3	Peace	2. 64, 65, 6. 14, 15, 27.	24	Self-knowledge	4. 33, 35, 37 - 39, 42, 5. 16, 13. 5, 6.
4	Sincerity	3. 32, 12. 18 – 21.	25	Self-analysis	2. 29, 30, 13. 33, 34
5	Sympathy	16. 1 – 3.	26	Universal truth	2. 26, 27, 7. 4, 5, 9. 16, 17.
6	Concerns for others	3. 13.	27	Democratic decision making	18. 63.
7	Satisfaction	2. 54, 55, 4. 20.	28	Friendship	6. 7, 18. 64.
8	Patience	2.1 4, 12. 17	29	Devotion	2. 14, 3. 30, 5. 17, 6. 47, 7. 17, 29, 30, 8. 7, 14, 11. 55, 12. 8, 18. 57, 62. 65, 66.
9	Tolerance	5. 20, 23, 9. 25, 12. 17.	30	Knowledge	2. 29, 3. 28, 4. 24, 5. 13, 6. 29, 8. 13, 9. 15, 12. 3, 13. 34, 14. 19, 18. 49.
10	Respect for all religion	9. 32.	31	Universal, self-existent truth	2. 24, 25.
11	Study of one's own self	2. 11, 29.	32	Sense of discrimination between true and false	2. 52.
12	Power of concentration	2. 42, 44, 45.	33	Obedience	2. 7.
13	Self-control	2. 38, 45, 56, 57, 61, 3. 7, 5. 10.	34	Self-respect	2. 33, 37.
14	Discipline	3. 3, 4, 4. 34, 6. 17.	35	Endurance	2. 14, 5. 23
15	Cultivation of virtues opposed to the sins	14. 19, 20, 16. 1, 5.	36	Freedom from deadly	10. 3.

				sins	
16	Equanimity and Equality	2. 15, 5. 18, 6. 8, 9, 29, 30, 18. 20	37	Self-sacrifice	5. 11, 12.
17	Faithfulness	2. 7, 3. 35, 6. 25, 30, 8. 14, 10.14.	38	Justice	9. 32.
18	Self-confidence	6. 24, 25, 2. 2, 3	39	Courage	2. 3.
19	Respect for others	2. 7, 4. 11.	40	Self-help	6. 5, 6, 7.
20	Punctuality	2. 66	41	Proper utilization of time	2. 2, 8. 5, 7.
21	Duty including loyalty to duty	2. 31, 33, 34.	42	Regularity	2. 37.

Values in teacher and student relationship from the perspective of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita

The Gita is conversation between student and teacher. Between the seeker and the one with the knowledge and each chapter is driven by asking Krishna something. Yoga is passed down from the students to teacher. Although reading the texts alone can be beneficial and can start someone on the path, nothing compare to the insight you receive from a teacher. The information is like a piece of coal, and it is shaped and refined through the entire mind that holds it. The diamond of knowledge a teacher finally passes down to you has come to them through their teachers, and their teacher and so on.

Some of the values which draw the light on importance of teacher –student relationship are following:

- Value of devotion
- Remove egoism
- Help to make person responsible
- Help to realize the duties
- Inculcate the value of belief
- Value of respect
- Obedience
- Act upon wisely
- Remove weakness

- Have patience
- Obedience of duties
- Needed for search of truth

Findings

Bhagavad Gita mainly emphasizes on knowledge, karma and devotion. Jnanayoga, the path of knowledge advocates oneself to follow the path of true knowledge. The knowledge of true identity of oneself i.e. Kshetra and Kshetrajna, which is body and soul respectively. Then Gita talks about the Bhaktiyoga, the yoga of devotion. Devotion or Bhakti is the most important of all the discipline of God realization. True devotion in which all sense of egoism and the senses which attached to the material objects becomes dissolved and only the thought of God remains in the mind. It is possible only for those who are able to control their senses, stabilize their minds, cultivate purity and perform their obligatory duties in the midst of society and their families.

The most important in all is the karmayoga, the yoga of action. Action with the selfish motive is inferior to that performed with equilibrium of mind. Negligence of duties incurs sin. Action without a selfish motive leads to the attainment of equal mindedness or 'Sthitpragya' or 'yoga'. One who is regular in his duty, regularity, sincerely and enthusiastically attain perfection here as well as hereafter, ensure salvation. Karmayoga is most relevant in the present scenario. Now –a- days students want to pass exams without hard work, people want good salaries without any work, and everybody wants improvement without doing any significant work. The result is in the form of multiple problems of stress and strain, tension, frustration etc. The selfless work and work without the desire for fruit makes one efficient. The Bhagavad Gita encourages one to perform one's obligatory duties as a sacrificial offering to God and not to turn our back upon them. It explains how delusion arises and how one become bound to present conditions, suggesting the various alternatives that are available to one to escape from them. It can be concluded that Shrimad Bhagavad Gita is most relevant for value inculcation. It helps to know the virtues and defects of oneself.

Moral values are standards of good and evil, which given an individual's behavior and choices. An individual with high moral values typically displays characteristics of integrity, courage, respect, honesty and compassion. Various methods as discussed in the present study can be used to change the attitude towards moral values. Methods include the realization of the identity; increase the tolerance power, regular and proper duties. do selfless action, self - satisfaction, control on senses, devotion to God, be courageous, take personal responsibilities,

be patient, be willing to serve, take guidance, add value to the world, destruction of desires and passion, keeping customs and traditions as it is, have fidelity, follow the discipline of meditation, destruction of demonian nature, penance of speech, motivation etc.

Out of 700 verses of sacred book of Bhagavad Gita investigator selected the 141 verses which will helps to inculcate the values among students. Student - teacher relationship from the perspective of Bhagavad Gita should have value of devotion, help to remove the egoism, it inculcates the love, care and affection. Let the student free as Arjuna was finally left to decide himself whether to fight or not. It removes the weakness of the students to take right decision. If teacher behaves like a friend it inculcates the value of friendship and helps to draw out the doubts of the students without any hesitation. As it is shown in the Bhagavad Gita that main role is of the Lord Krishna, he is the teacher of Arjuna. As Lord Krishna taught the Arjuna but not compelled him to fight, Lord gives him the right direction to choose the right path. So it is necessary for teachers, don't impose hard rules on the students to complete their work but let them free to do their work with free mind and remove their confusion and problems whenever required.

Conclusion

The Bhagavad Gita is considered highly relevant for inculcating moral values such as integrity, courage, respect, honesty, and compassion. Methods to change attitudes towards moral values include self-realization, tolerance, performing regular duties, selfless action, self-satisfaction, sense control, devotion to God, personal responsibility, patience, willingness to serve, guidance, adding value to the world, and destruction of desires.

The study selected 141 verses from the Bhagavad Gita that aid in inculcating values among students. The student-teacher relationship, viewed through the lens of the Bhagavad Gita, should embody devotion, removal of egoism, and cultivation of love, care, and affection. Like Arjuna, students should be allowed to make their own decisions, with teachers providing guidance without imposing strict rules. This approach helps remove students' weaknesses and doubts, fostering a friendly and supportive learning environment.

In conclusion, the Bhagavad Gita offers profound insights and practical guidance for value education, promoting moral development, and shaping character through its teachings on knowledge, devotion, and selfless action.

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